

ARETE

Augmented Reality Interactive Educational System

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Abstract

Augmented reality (AR) refers to computer-mediated reality that changes a person's perception by adding data to the real environment. It's considered to be a very effective tool for education. The EU-funded ARETE project aims to build a Europe-wide competitive ecosystem that supports fast dissemination of augmented learning content. ARETE will focus on three pilot studies in STEM, English literacy skills and positive behaviour intervention. The human-centred attitude of the project will boost innovation and creativity, making Europe a world leader of AR and virtual reality in education. The ARETE ecosystem concept will sustain innovation and improve the performance of existing products or services.

Objectives

Objective 1: To develop and evaluate the effectiveness of an interactive AR content toolkit

ARETE will ensure that an interactive AR content toolkit will be developed for the creation of 3D objects based on AR standards. ARETE toolkit will design and implement the AR/3D data repositories for storage and retrieval during the lifespan of the project and beyond. ARETE will create standards-compliant AR/3D data infrastructures for educational purposes to ensure applicability, reproducibility, interoperability, accessibility and sustainability.

Objective 2: To apply human-centred interaction design for ARETE ecosystem (linked to WP3 & WP5)

ARETE will identify, update and integrate on an ongoing basis, user-based insights into designing and developing AR content for the pilot studies.

The interaction design within ARETE will enable different stakeholders to use the AR technology with ease and positive experience for meeting their needs, preferences, and goals, leading to its high adoption and stimulating its creative uses.

Objective 3: To pilot and evaluate the effectiveness of AR interactive technologies (linked to WP4, WP5)

The ARETE ecosystem, which comprises of AR emerging technologies, main platform, training platform, mobile app and a multi-lingual interface will be piloted. Students and EU citizens (i.e. 3000+ in EU member states) will participate in three different pilot studies. The ecosystem will be piloted at “ γ -phase”, focusing on assessing the impact of the AR content within professional and private contexts (students, teachers, educational technologists). Stakeholders will utilise the effectiveness of the ecosystem through the evaluation of specific skill sets and behaviours (STEM; English literacy skills; and impact of Positive Behaviour Support in Schools – PBIS).

Objective 4: To communicate, disseminate and exploit the project results (linked to WP1 & WP6)

ARETE promotes project awareness and progress details to the wider and targeted markets. In this light, a scientific, societal and economic focused dissemination and market outreach campaign is well-formulated. In this context, we adapt a three-phase dissemination and market out-reach approach to achieve this objective for take up for beyond the life of the project.

Pilots

From three pilot studies, ARETE collects baseline data in terms of user needs and education practices to inform the pedagogical content of the ARETE toolkit.

ARETE aims to:

- develop, integrate and disseminate interactive technology via AR methods and tools to create and connect existing digital systems, and to build a pan-European

competitive ecosystem that supports fast dissemination of augmented learning content to a wide audience.

- strengthen the research and industrial capacities in Europe to develop future interactive devices and content for education.
- support the existing effort to seek opportunities offered by multiuser interactions with AR technologies in education.

Over three different primary school education pilots, ARETE aims to enable disruptive innovation of AR for interactions, access, and distribution of content to enhance European innovation in the field of education.

Pilot 1: Using Augmented Reality to facilitate teaching English literacy skills

Pilot 1 redevelops an existing WordsWorthLearning (WWL) digital programme into an app containing Augmented Reality (AR) - to facilitate teaching English language reading and spelling skills to struggling students. The aim is to utilise AR based teaching and learning technologies to make both teaching and learning of the English language more accessible and successful for those teachers and students engaged in the process. [More info](#)

Pilot 2: Augmented Reality as an Efficient Tool for STEM Information Retention

The second Pilot focuses on the innovative and exciting way of learning geometry and geography through visualisation and interaction of Augmented Reality applications. By understanding and engaging with abstract objects, pupils have the opportunity to develop both their spatial and visual cognition while learning through critical thinking. Pilot 2 is based on the CleverBooks app, which provides STEM-oriented global curriculum-based teaching and learning solutions for primary education. [More info](#)

Pilot 3: Augmented Reality for promoting behaviour management and self-management

Pilot 3 focuses on the development of AR solutions to be embedded within the context of the framework of Positive Behaviour Interventions & Support, an intervention model that actively supports the implementation of Evidence-Based Practices for classroom and school discipline. The pilot is expected to be delivered to more than 500 students across Italy and the Netherlands.